

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

EU FarmBook User Manual

Version 1.0

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1 Introduction

The EU FarmBook is being developed to test a big idea: Can all of the tangible outputs of EU-funded research and innovation projects be brought together and organized in one user-friendly platform to help get practical knowledge into the hands of the farmers, foresters and advisors across Europe who need it most?

The challenges to doing this are great – data(base) quality and compatibility issues, language barriers, and intergenerational considerations to name a few – but we believe that the future of agriculture and forestry innovation in Europe is digital, and requires a vastly increased and improved digital exchange of knowledge between EU regions and Member States, as well as between different agricultural stakeholders: researchers, policymakers, SMEs, advisors, farmers and foresters.

EU FarmBook is the result of two EU-funded Horizon 2020 “sister” projects, EURAKNOS (<https://euraknos.eu/>) and EUREKA (<https://h2020eureka.eu/>), which have brought together diverse partners from 28 organizations across 16 countries to work together using a multi-actor approach. Please visit the websites and check out [this short video](#) to learn more.

2 Creating a new account

For browsing the knowledge database and reading articles you don't need an account. When you want to join into social actions like voting, commenting, and creating discussions, you will need to create an account.

To do so, we navigate to the LOGIN button at the top right:

Here we see the screen to log in to an account, but we don't have an account yet. We navigate to the 'Sign up here' link:

This brings us to the sign-up page, where you can fill in all the data we need to create an account. Once done, please read and accept the [Terms and conditions](#), then click 'Sign up'.

EU FARMBOOK Pilot version Topics Search for articles, experts, threads... About us Help LOG IN EN

Sign Up

Do you already have an account? [Log in here.](#)

USERNAME * YOUR AGE

FIRST NAME * LAST NAME *

E-MAIL ADDRESS *

PASSWORD *

YOUR PROFESSION
-- Please select a value --

YOUR MAIN INTEREST
-- Please select a value --

I Accept The [Terms And Conditions.](#) *

Sign up

After clicking 'Sign up' you will receive an email from noreply@eufarmbook.eu with a confirmation link. If you don't see an email within a few minutes, please check your spam folder.

EU FARMBOOK Pilot version Topics Search for articles, experts, threads... About us Help LOG IN EN

Sign Up

Do you already have an account? [Log in here.](#)

Please check your mailbox!

You will receive a confirmation email to finish up your registration. If you don't receive an email, please do check your spamfolder.

EU FARMBOOK
Pilot version

EU FarmBook is a collection of vetted best practices for farmers & foresters. All content in the library is provided by Horizon research projects. Learn more about this project on [our website](#)

ABOUT US
About EU FarmBook
Help
Contact us
Contribute

FOLLOW US
Youtube
Twitter

EU FarmBook has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No's 817863 and 862790.

The email will look something like this – just click the blue confirmation link:

Now the account is confirmed and you can login (see next chapter).

3 Logging in

Now to Log in we again navigate to the top right, 'LOG IN' button.

This brings us to the login screen. Here you can fill in your chosen email and password and press 'Log in'. You will then be redirected to the homepage, and now you will see your username at the top right.

4 Selecting a different language and other translation features

○ Switching language

To make the platform more accessible for everyone in Europe we support most of the commonly spoken EU languages (currently 13 + English, with more to be added in future):

- Danish
- Dutch
- English (default)
- Estonian
- French
- German
- Greek
- Hungarian
- Italian
- Lithuanian
- Polish
- Romanian
- Slovenian
- Spanish

The default language for the platform is English. All automatic translations are based on English.

To use the platform in different languages, we can navigate to the top right corner of the website and next to the 'LOG IN' button you will find the language selector. The currently selected language is indicated, 'EN' (English) by default. To select a different language, hover over it and a popup will appear containing all the available options for languages. Select your preferred language and the platform will update automatically.

■ Automatic translations

While much of the text on the main pages and menus has been manually translated by EUREKA partners with the help of POEditor (<https://poeditor.com>), most of the content itself (including the titles of articles, their descriptions and keywords) is translated by a translation service called DeepL (<https://www.deepl.com/translator>).

■ Translate user content

For user-generated content such as comments we don't translate these to your selected language. But you have the option to translate this content automatically through automatic translation by DeepL. The following sections explain how.

■ Translating comments

Underneath a comment you will see a button called 'Translate comment' (or the equivalent phrase in your selected language – automatically translated) that allows you to translate the comment to the language you have currently selected in the language selector at the top right.

This is the result:

■ Translating threads

When we navigate to a 'Threads & discussions' detail page (found in the 'Community' sections), we can also see a 'Translate Thread' button. When pressed this will translate the thread to the language you have currently selected in the language selector at the top right.

This is the result:

How to use whitehall method?

a month ago
by NAKTEST

Hi, we just started our project, and we need recomendation. Csak most kezttük a projektet, minden tanácsot szivesen veszünk

Translated from Hungarian by DeepL

Hi, we just started our project, and we need recomendation. We just started our project, and we need recomendation

5 Browsing different topics

The EU Farmbook platform is full of a wide range of content that we call “knowledge objects”, but how do you browse between all the different topics?

First we have the homepage, where we can immediately find the 6 main, broader topics. These topics are:

- Forestry
- Livestock
- Crop farming
- Environment
- Society
- Economics

We can also navigate using the menu at the top left. If you hover over 'Topics' the following menu will appear, which has the same main categories:

Now let us select a topic, for example Forestry. We will be directed to an overview page containing all knowledge objects for that specific topic:

Here you have a lot of options of what you can do:

- You can use the search bar to search for a specific knowledge object

- You can use the menu to switch between the Content, Community or Experts specific for this topic.

- All Content

- Community

- Experts (note that this feature and service is still being developed)

- You can also sort the knowledge objects in a number of ways:
 - By relevance
 - From A-Z
 - From Z-A
 - Recent
 - Oldest

- You also have an option to change the view of the content from a tile view to a more compact list view:
 - Tile view

- List view

- If you are at the end of the list and want to see more results (if available) just press the ‘Show more’ button and more tiles or list items will appear.

- You can also see the total number of results for each specific topic

6 Searching the knowledge database

The EU FarmBook wouldn't be much of a knowledge platform without a powerful search engine, of course! You can do a global search of the knowledge database, which gives more possibilities to filter your results and find the knowledge objects most of interest to you.

A global search starts at the homepage, where you have a prominent search bar in the middle of the screen. Here you can specify which topic you are interested in at the left, followed by your search term in the box to the right. By pressing the 'Search' button or pressing the enter/return key on your keyboard you will be directed to a page where all results for your search will be listed.

Now let's look at all the options we have available:

- First of all, you are reminded of the search term entered above the list of results. This search term is also highlighted in the title and description of a knowledge object.

- You can see the number of search results for your search

- You can also sort the knowledge objects in a number of ways:
 - By relevance

- From A-Z
- From Z-A
- Recent
- Oldest

The screenshot shows the EU FarmBook search results page for the query 'cow'. At the top, the navigation bar includes the 'EU FARMBOOK Pilot version' logo, a 'Topics' dropdown menu, a search bar containing 'cow', and links for 'About us', 'Help', 'joachim', and 'EN'. Below the navigation bar, there is a 'RETURN TO OVERVIEW' button. The main heading is 'Search results for 'cow'', with a sub-heading 'A TOTAL OF 31 RESULTS'. A red arrow points to a 'SORT BY relevancy' dropdown menu that is open, showing options: 'Relevancy', 'A-Z', 'Z-A', 'Recent', and 'Recent'. The search results are displayed in a grid. The first result is a video titled 'Farm system focusing on cows health and welfare', categorized under 'LIVESTOCK' and 'VIDEO'. The video thumbnail shows a cow in a milking parlor. The description states: 'Usually in Poland cows stay inside cowsheds all year around. Presented farm, even with a large scale of production...'. Below the description are 'KEYWORDS: COWS HEALTH MILK PRODUCTION DAIRY'. To the right of the search results is a sidebar with filter options: 'Content type' (Content, Community, Experts), 'Topic', 'Subtopic', 'Category', 'Language', and 'Location', each with a dropdown arrow.

- As explained above in Browsing, you also have an option to change the view of the results from a tile view to a list view:
 - Tile view

- List view

- If you reach the end of the list and want to see more results (if available), just press 'Load more' and they will appear.

The screenshot shows the EU FarmBook website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo 'EU FARMBOOK Pilot version', a 'Topics' dropdown menu, a search bar containing the word 'COW', and links for 'About us', 'Help', a user profile 'joachim', and a language selector 'EN'. Below the navigation bar, a search result is displayed. It features a thumbnail image of a cow in a field. The title of the result is 'Nedap GPS cow positioning technology - case study'. Below the title, there are tags for 'LIVESTOCK' and 'VIDEO'. The description reads: 'Innovation for Agriculture visited dairy farms in Sweden and Holland to see sensor technologies in practice. The farmers in this video intro...'. There are two sets of keywords: the first set includes 'FEED', 'CATTLE', and 'MILK PRODUCTION'; the second set includes 'DAIRY FARM', 'GPS', and 'TECHNOLOGY'. A 'Load more' button is positioned below the search result. At the bottom of the page, there is a footer section with three columns. The first column contains the EU FarmBook logo and a description: 'EU FarmBook is a collection of vetted best practices for farmers & foresters. All content in the library is provided by Horizon research projects. Learn more about this project on [our website](#)'. The second column, titled 'ABOUT US', lists links for 'About EU FarmBook', 'Help', 'Contact us', and 'Contribute'. The third column, titled 'FOLLOW US', lists 'Youtube' and 'Twitter'. To the right of the footer, there is a paragraph of text: 'EU FarmBook has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No's 817863 and 862790.'

- In the right-hand column you have a set of more advanced filters that allow you to filter the results more in depth. Here are the filters and a short explanation of each one:
 - Content type - Refers to the 3 main sections or page types in the EU FarmBook: (normal) 'Content', the 'Community' for threads & discussions, and 'Experts'
 - Topic - The 6 broad topics, for example 'Forestry' and 'Environment'
 - Subtopic - A list of a bit more than 20 terms used by the [EIP-AGRI](#) to categorize information in their system
 - Category - This refers to the format of the knowledge object: Document, Audio, Infographic, Presentation, Video, or Image
 - Language - Only show knowledge objects, for example videos or presentations, that are spoken or written in the selected language or set of languages that you select. (*Note that currently all of the titles and descriptions are written in English for consistency in the database, but this will change with future improvements to the EU FarmBook*)
 - Location - Select content that is associated with or was applied in a certain country

When you select a filter, or multiple filters, it/they will be shown above in a list – these are all the ‘Active filters’. You can remove them by clicking on the selected filter again (un-check the box) or by clicking the ‘X’ on the active filter label. There is also an option to clear all filters.

7 Different types of content

The EU FarmBook has 3 main types of content or pages:

- Content - contains all the knowledge objects
- Community - These are threads and discussions created by users, where you read and/or take part in social activities like commenting on someone else's discussion or creating a new discussion.
- Experts - These are users with expertise about one or multiple topics who have the choice to make their contact info available so they can be reached for advice.

8 Taking a closer look at a knowledge object

If we click on a knowledge object tile or list item, we enter a detailed view of that knowledge object. This page contains a lot of information and features.

On the page you can read a detailed description of the knowledge object – what's it about? Who is the author / expert? All the important details. Now let's have a look at all the info you can find on a detail page. The following list corresponds to the labels on the image below (next page):

1. Vote counter: here you can like with the up-/down arrows a knowledge object; there is also a count of how many likes the article has.
2. Comment counter: here you can see how many comments the article has. If you click on this label, you will scroll to the comments section.
3. Share popup: if you hover over this button, it will show a list of all sharing options (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, or copy the link)
4. The 'More info' section gives details like location, purpose or filetype.
5. Related links: here you can find links to other websites related to the article
6. Author/Contributor: Below the title you can see the author or authors of the knowledge object (in some cases this can be a project). Clicking on an author name will bring you to a detail-page for that author, who may also be one of the voluntary registered 'Experts'.
7. Below the description is the media section, where a preview of the content itself appears, including videos, PDFs, presentations, audio files,... If it's a PDF document, you will have the option to download it.
8. 'Knowledge object metadata': this table is more for developers than for users but can be expanded ('Show more') to view all of the metadata stored in the database for that KO.
9. Keywords: A list of all the keywords that have been added by the contributor or by the EU FarmBook team for a KO.
10. Comments section: here you can post new comments and upvote, downvote, or respond to other comments; you can also delete or edit comments that *you* have posted.
11. Finally, at the very bottom you will find 'Related content' that may be of interest.

The screenshot displays the EU FarmBook interface for a video article. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'EU FARMBOOK' logo, a search bar, and user information. The article title is 'Farm system focusing on cows health and welfare'. A video player is embedded in the article, showing a man talking to cows. Below the video is a metadata section with fields for 'langcode' and 'title'. A 'Keywords' section lists 'COWS HEALTH', 'MILK PRODUCTION', and 'DAIRY'. A comment section is visible below the keywords, with a 'Comment' button. On the right side, there is a sidebar with 'More info' and 'Related links' sections. Red arrows with numbers 1 through 11 point to various elements: 1 (likes), 2 (comments), 3 (share), 4 (More info), 5 (Related links), 6 (author), 7 (text), 8 (video player), 9 (metadata), 10 (comment box), and 11 (related content).

The 'Related content' section features three article thumbnails. The first is 'Sheep production system in Romania' with a 'LIVESTOCK' icon and 'PRESENTATION' label. The second is 'Euro Dairy - improving the viability and sustainability of milk production in Europe' with a 'LIVESTOCK' icon and 'AUDIO' label. The third is 'Sowing grasses and legumes a cross' with a 'LIVESTOCK' icon and 'VIDEO' label. Each thumbnail includes a brief description and a list of keywords.

9 How to comment on a knowledge object

Every knowledge object gives us the option to comment or read comments from other users. Comments can be placed on knowledge objects as well as Threads & discussions.

○ Creating a comment

To create a comment, go to the comment input field. Enter the comment you like to publish. You have some basic text-formatting options like making the font **bold**, underlined, *italic* or adding a hyperlink. When finished creating your comment, just press the 'Comment' and it will be published.

○ Editing or deleting a comment

To edit or delete your comment, hover over the 3 dots and a popup appears. 'Edit' will bring you back to the input field where you can make changes and re- publish your comment.

Related content

To delete your comment, again hover over the 3 dots and press 'Delete' in the popup. When pressed, the comment will be deleted immediately.

10 Logging out

To log out of your account, navigate to the top right where you can see your name. Hover with your mouse over it and the 'Log out' button will appear. Just press it and you will be logged out of your account.

11 Thanks for using EU Farmbook!

We hope this simple visual guide has been useful. If you experience any issues with the site or wish to leave feedback, please send a message to eufarmbook@ugent.be. We are a small team at the moment, but we'll do our best to get back to you!

12 Troubleshooting

■ Forgot your password?

In case you forgot your password, you can navigate to the 'Forgot your password?' link.

Here you can fill in the email address you used to create your account. Once done, press the 'Reset' button. You will receive an email with instructions to create your new password.

The email you receive will look something like this. To reset your password just click the blue link:

The email will redirect you to a screen where you can fill in a new password and submit it by pressing the 'Renew password' button. Now you can try to log in with your new password.